

Effect of Hydroxyurea on Transfusion Requirements in Pediatric β -Thalassemia: A Quasi-Experimental Study

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Abstract

Objective: This study evaluates the effect of hydroxyurea on transfusion burden in Pakistani children with transfusion-dependent β thalassemia.

Material and Methods: A single-center, quasi-experimental (single arm pre–post) study was conducted at the Pediatric Medicine Department of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad. Sixty consecutively recruited pediatric patients (aged 1–16 years) with transfusion-dependent β thalassemia received hydroxyurea 15 mg/kg/day for six months. Baseline variables included age, sex, thalassemia subtype, iron chelation status, and number of transfusions in the preceding six months. Monthly follow-up assessed clinical status and complete blood count; transfusions were administered when hemoglobin <10 g/dL or clinically indicated.

Results: Sixty patients (mean age 7.03 ± 2.73 years; 60% male) completed the study. The median number of transfusions decreased from 8.00 (interquartile range [IQR] 5.00-11.25) in the six months before therapy to 7.00 (IQR 3.75-10.00) afterwards (median change -1.00; $p = 0.0001$). The median transfusion interval increased from 22.50 days (IQR 16.05-36.00) to 25.70 days (IQR 18.00-48.75) (median change +2.95 days; $p < 0.0001$). Hemoglobin rose from 7.47 ± 0.81 g/dL to 8.33 ± 1.01 g/dL (median change +0.70 g/dL; $p < 0.0001$). Seventeen patients (28.3%, 95% CI 17.5-41.4%) were responders.

Conclusion: A 6-month course of HU at 15 mg/kg/day was associated with a clinically meaningful reduction in transfusion burden and improved hemoglobin in pediatric β -thalassemia, with acceptable short-term safety. These findings support HU as an adjunct to regular transfusions in monitored settings, while underscoring the need for larger genotype-stratified trials and long-term follow-up.

Keywords: Hydroxyurea; β -Thalassemia; Transfusion; Pediatrics, Pakistan

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Introduction

Beta (β)-thalassemia major is a hereditary hemoglobinopathy caused by absent or markedly reduced β -globin synthesis, leading to severe anemia that typically requires lifelong packed red blood cell (PRBC) transfusions and iron chelation to prevent morbidity from iron overload.¹⁻²

The transfusion-dependent course places a heavy clinical and economic burden on families and health systems and increases the risk of transfusion-transmitted infections, iron-related organ damage, and reduced quality of life.³⁻⁵ Despite advances in transfusion safety and chelation, strategies that safely reduce transfusion frequency remain a critical unmet need in many low- and middle-income settings.³⁻⁴

Hydroxyurea (HU), an oral ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor, raises fetal hemoglobin (HbF) and ameliorates ineffective erythropoiesis; it is well established in sickle cell disease and has shown promise in nontransfusion-dependent and some transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia cohorts.^{6,7} Recent randomized and observational studies and meta-analyses report variable responses: some trials report HU reduces transfusion burden in a meaningful minority (≈ 30 -40%), while systematic reviews highlight heterogeneity in design, dosing, and outcome measures and call for better quality evidence in transfusion-dependent populations.⁸⁻¹⁰ Several Cochrane reviews and a 2022 randomized double-

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blind trial provide contemporary data but stop short of universal endorsement for routine HU in transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia.^{7,10,8} Moreover, local genotype distributions, baseline transfusion practices, and health-system factors may modify effectiveness and safety.^{8,6,9}

These inconsistencies necessitate a need for context-specific, prospectively collected data in pediatric populations.^{11,4} Given the disease burden locally and the relatively low cost and oral route of HU, evaluating its utility as an adjunct to transfusion regimens in Pakistani pediatric practice is a pragmatic priority.^{12,4} This study will generate real-world evidence on transfusion reduction, safety, and operational feasibility, informing immediate clinical guidance and possible larger randomized trials. ability to pump blood effectively, leading to decreased cardiac output and systemic perfusion.² The primary objective was to determine whether hydroxyurea (15 mg/kg/day) reduces the number of packed red blood cell transfusions received by pediatric patients with transfusion-dependent β thalassemia during six months of therapy compared with the six months prior to initiation.

Material and Methods

single-center, quasi-experimental (single arm pre–post) study was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad. The study period started on 1st September 2021 and spanned 12 months till 31st August 2022. Consecutive pediatric patients aged 1–16 years with transfusion-dependent β thalassemia were recruited. Inclusion criteria were documented transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia (by hemoglobin electrophoresis/genotype or clinical history), ≥ 2 PRBC transfusions in the prior 6 months, and informed consent from parent/guardian. Exclusion criteria included prior hydroxyurea therapy within six months, severe infection, uncontrolled hepatic or renal dysfunction, pregnancy or lactation in adolescents, hypersensitivity to hydroxyurea, and baseline neutropenia (absolute neutrophil count $< 1.5 \times 10^9/L$) or thrombocytopenia (platelets $< 100 \times 10^9/L$).

After baseline assessment, each participant received hydroxyurea (HU) at 15 mg/kg once daily plus folic acid 5 mg daily for six months. Monthly follow-up included clinical evaluation and complete blood count. Transfusions were administered when hemoglobin fell below 10 g/dL or clinical need arose. Adverse events were monitored and graded; HU was withheld or dose-reduced for severe cytopenias. At six months, transfusion frequency, interval, adverse events, and hemoglobin were compared with the six-month pretreatment period. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants or their legal guardians prior to inclusion.

Baseline variables recorded were age, sex, age at diagnosis, age at first transfusion, number of transfusions in the

previous 6 months (from records), baseline transfusion interval (days), iron chelation status (yes/no; single vs. combined agent), thalassemia category (major or intermedia), and baseline complete blood count. Follow-up data included monthly hemoglobin, transfusion dates, and adverse events.

All data were entered into a password-protected electronic database with coded identifiers. Reduction in the number of packed red blood cell transfusions during the treatment period was the primary outcome measure. The secondary outcome measures were any change in the transfusion interval, hemoglobin kinetics, responder rate (patient achieving $\geq 50\%$ reduction in number of transfusions during the six-month post-hydroxyurea period compared with the six-month pretreatment baseline), and incidence of adverse events.

Continuous variables are described using mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median (IQR); categorical variables are presented as frequencies and percentages. Primary analysis compared the total number of transfusions in the six months before and after hydroxyurea using the Wilcoxon signed rank test due to nonnormal distribution. Changes in transfusion interval and hemoglobin were analyzed similarly. The proportion of responders ($\geq 50\%$ reduction) was calculated with 95% confidence intervals (CI). Negative binomial regression modelled post-treatment transfusion counts, with pre-treatment transfusions and demographic variables as covariates. Logistic regression explored predictors of responder status. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ (two-sided). Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics v26.

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad (Approval No. 48/ERC/FMU2020-21/146; dated August 21, 2021). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants or their legal guardians prior to inclusion. All data were deidentified and stored in password-protected files accessible only to the investigators to ensure participant confidentiality. A single-center, quasi-experimental (single arm pre–post) study was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad. The study period started on 1st September 2021 and spanned 12 months till 31st August 2022.

Results

Sixty patients (N=60) were included. The mean age was 7.03 ± 2.73 years, and 36 (60.0%) were male. The majority had β -thalassemia major (46/60, 76.7%), and 53/60 (88.3%) were on iron chelation therapy at baseline. Mean hemoglobin was 7.47 ± 0.81 g/dL [median 7.50, interquartile range (IQR) 7.00–8.10]. The pre-HU transfusion burden (6-month total) averaged 8.83 ± 4.07 units (median 8.00, IQR 5.00–11.25) (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study participants (n = 60)

Characteristic	Value
Age, years	7.03 ± 2.73
Male sex, n (%)	36 (60.0)
Female sex, n (%)	24 (40.0)
β-thalassemia major, n (%)	46 (76.7)
β-thalassemia intermedia, n (%)	14 (23.3)
Receiving iron chelation, n (%)	53 (88.3)
Baseline hemoglobin, g/dL, mean±standard deviation	7.47 ± 0.81
Transfusion episodes in prior 6 months, median (IQR)	8.00 (5.00-11.25)

IQR = Interquartile Range

Complete paired data were available for all participants. The median number of packed red blood cell transfusions over 6 months decreased from 8.00 (IQR 5.00–11.25) before hydroxyurea therapy to 7.00 (IQR 3.75–10.00) after treatment. The median within-patient change was -1.00 transfusions (IQR -3.00 to 0.25). This reduction was statistically significant (Table 2).

Table 2: Primary outcomes before and after hydroxyurea therapy for 6 months (n = 60)

Statistic	Value
Pre-HU transfusions (median, IQR)	8.00 (5.00-11.25)
Post-HU transfusions (median, IQR)	7.00 (3.75-10.00)
Median change (post - pre)	-1.00 (-3.00-0.25)
Wilcoxon signed-rank	W = 238.5, p = 0.0001
Percent reduction (median, IQR)	12.7% (-1.79% -50.0%)

IQR = Interquartile Range

Transfusion interval: The median interval between transfusions increased from 22.50 days (IQR 16.05-36.00) to 25.70 days (IQR 18.00-48.75), with a median paired change of +2.95 days. This difference was statistically significant (Table 3).

Table 3: Transfusion interval (days) (Pre vs. Post Hydroxyurea Treatment for 6 months) (n = 60)

Statistic	Value
Pre-hydroxyurea transfusion interval (median, IQR)	22.50 (16.05-36.00) days
Post-hydroxyurea transfusion interval (median, IQR)	25.70 (18.00-48.75) days
Median change (post - pre)	+2.95 days (0.225-15.00)
Wilcoxon signed-rank	W = 191.0, p < 0.0001

Hemoglobin kinetics: Mean hemoglobin increased from 7.47 ± 0.81 g/dL to 8.33 ± 1.01 g/dL. The within-patient rise was +0.70 g/dL (p < 0.0001), and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test confirmed a highly significant improvement (W = 0.0, p < 0.0001). The rank-biserial correlation was 1.00. Figure 1 illustrates these paired hemoglobin trajectories, showing a consistent upward shift across the cohort.

Seventeen of 60 patients (28.3%) achieved ≥50% reduction in transfusion requirements (95% CI 17.5-41.4). Figure 2 shows the distribution of responders vs. non-responders. Figure 2: Proportion of Responders and Non-Responders after Six Months of Hydroxyurea Therapy.

In exploratory negative binomial regression, only baseline transfusion frequency was associated with post-treatment transfusion count (incidence rate ratio 1.13, 95% CI 1.05-1.21; $p=0.0007$). Age, sex, iron chelation status, and thalassemia subtype were not statistically significant. Exploratory logistic regression for responder status yielded no significant predictors; because only 17 children met the responder definition, these estimates were imprecise and are not emphasized (Table 4).

Table 4: Exploratory negative binomial model for post-treatment transfusion count

Predictor	IRR	95% CI	p-value
Baseline transfusion frequency	1.13	1.05-1.21	0.0007
Age	1.01	0.91-1.12	0.86
Iron chelation (yes)	0.96	0.39-2.36	0.933
Male sex	1.05	0.59-1.86	0.876
β -thalassemia intermedia vs major	1.31	0.66-2.61	0.44

In the multivariable logistic regression model for responder status, no covariate reached statistical significance. The estimated odds ratios were imprecise, with wide confidence intervals. Model discrimination was modest (AUC = 0.644), and calibration was acceptable (Hosmer-Lemeshow $\chi^2 = 5.189$, $p = 0.737$) (Table 5).

Table 5: Multivariable Logistic Regression for Responder ($\geq 50\%$ Reduction)

Predictor	OR	95% CI	p-value
Transfusion frequency (pretreatment)	0.99	0.857-1.145	0.8966
Age	1.06	0.849-1.325	0.6056
Iron chelation (yes)	2.674	0.269-26.58	0.4013
Male vs. Female	1.912	0.535-6.831	0.3186
Thalassemia: Intermedia vs. Major	0.435	0.081-2.329	0.3308

Discussion

In this study, we evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of the In this single-center quasi-experimental study, hydroxyurea given at a fixed dose of 15 mg/kg/day for 6 months was associated with a statistically significant reduction in transfusion requirements, a longer transfusion interval, and improved hemoglobin concentration in children with transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia. However, the

magnitude of benefit at the cohort level was modest, with a median reduction of one transfusion over 6 months, while a more substantial response was observed in only a subset of patients. These findings suggest that hydroxyurea may have a useful adjunctive role in selected patients, but they do not support uniform response across all children with transfusion-dependent disease.

These findings are consistent with previous studies showing that hydroxyurea can reduce transfusion burden in a proportion of patients with transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia, although the effect is heterogeneous. A randomized placebo-controlled trial reported clinically relevant response in a subset of patients and highlighted possible genotype-dependent variation in treatment effect.⁸ Similarly, meta-analyses and systematic reviews have concluded that hydroxyurea may benefit some transfusion-dependent patients, but the overall certainty of evidence remains limited by heterogeneity in study design, dosing strategies, outcome definitions, and transfusion thresholds.^{9,10,17} Regional studies, including Pakistani cohorts, have also described reduced transfusion requirements in selected children treated with hydroxyurea, supporting the practical relevance of this approach in South Asian settings.^{12,14,15}

The relatively low responder rate observed in the present study is also in keeping with the variable response patterns reported in the literature. Several factors may explain this finding. First, the response to hydroxyurea in β -thalassemia is likely influenced by underlying genetic and fetal hemoglobin-related determinants, including modifiers such as the Xmn1 polymorphism, which were not assessed in the present study.^{8,16} Second, the use of a fixed low-dose regimen may have limited the magnitude of response in some children, as dose-escalation approaches have shown greater benefit in selected populations.^{8,16} Third, the 6-month follow-up period may have been sufficient to detect early hematologic improvement but may not have captured the full therapeutic response in all patients. Finally, variation in baseline disease severity and transfusion burden may also contribute to differential treatment response across patients.^{9,10}

The findings have practical implications for pediatric thalassemia care in Pakistan. In resource-constrained settings, where safe blood availability, regular transfusion access, and long-term chelation remain ongoing challenges, even a modest reduction in transfusion burden may be clinically relevant for some families and treatment centers.³⁻

⁵ Hydroxyurea is orally administered, relatively inexpensive, and familiar to clinicians managing hemoglobinopathies, which enhances its feasibility as an adjunctive strategy.^{6,13}

At the same time, the modest average benefit observed in this study indicates that hydroxyurea should not be presented as a replacement for standard transfusion therapy. Rather, it may be considered an adjunct in appropriately monitored patients, with counseling that response is variable and that

some children may derive little transfusion-related benefit. Although a formal cost-effectiveness analysis was beyond the scope of this study, any reduction in transfusion frequency could potentially lessen direct treatment costs, travel burden, and the cumulative consequences of iron overload; this remains an important area for future evaluation.^{3-5,13}

This study has several strengths. It provides prospectively collected real-world data from a dedicated pediatric thalassemia setting, includes complete paired follow-up for all 60 participants, applies prespecified transfusion criteria, and evaluates both clinical outcomes and exploratory predictors of response. These features strengthen the internal consistency of the findings and increase their relevance to routine practice. However, the limitations are important. The single-arm pre-post design without a concurrent control group limits causal inference and leaves open the possibility of regression to the mean, secular trends, and changes in clinician transfusion practice. The study was conducted at a single center with a relatively small sample, which restricts generalizability. The regression analyses, particularly for responder status, should be interpreted cautiously because the limited number of responder events may have reduced model stability. In addition, genotype data, fetal hemoglobin levels, and longer-term outcomes were not available, limiting the ability to identify predictors of response and assess sustained benefit.

Future studies should build on these findings using multicenter designs, larger sample sizes, and longer follow-up periods. Randomized or well-controlled prospective studies are needed to better define the true magnitude of benefit attributable to hydroxyurea in transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia. Incorporation of genotype and pharmacogenomic markers may help identify children most likely to respond and support more individualized therapy. Comparative studies evaluating fixed-dose versus dose-escalated regimens, together with standardized transfusion protocols, would also be valuable. In Pakistan and similar settings, future research should additionally address cost-effectiveness, implementation feasibility, and long-term safety to better inform policy and clinical practice.

Conclusion

Hydroxyurea at a fixed dose of 15 mg/kg/day for 6 months was associated with a statistically significant but modest reduction in transfusion requirements, longer transfusion intervals, and improved hemoglobin levels in children with transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia. A clinically important reduction in transfusion burden was observed in a subset of patients, while short-term treatment was generally well tolerated. These findings support the use of hydroxyurea as an adjunct, rather than a replacement, to regular transfusion therapy in carefully monitored pediatric patients,

particularly in resource-constrained settings. Larger controlled studies with longer follow-up, dose optimization, and genotype-based stratification are needed to better define responders and establish long-term effectiveness and safety.

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